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Editor

Prof. Dr.M. Manimohan (Rtd)

Sree Sankaracharya University of Sanskrit, Kalady

dr.m.manimohan@gmail.com

Executive Editor

Prof. Dr.C.S.Sasikumar (Rtd.)

Sree Sankaracharya University of Sanskrit, Kalady

dr.sasikumarcs@gmail.com

Managing Editor

Prof. Dr.G.Narayanan

Sree Sankaracharya University of Sanskrit, Kalady

dr.g.narayanan@gmail.com

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Desamangalam Srikantha Variar - A Versatile Scholar

Dr.V.P.Udayakumar¹

This article is intended to introduce Desamangalam Srikantha Variar (SKV), author of the बालबोधिका (BB) commentary on शिशुपालधम् (।)

The Desamangalam Variyam, ancient family of Sanskrit scholars in the village of Desamangalam, was a centre of learning for the teaching and propagation of Sanskrit language and literature. The members of the family were traditionally teachers of the Zamorins of Calicut. The family of Desamangalam Vairiyars has produced several renowned scholars and poets. Most of them were called Srikantha or Rudra, two names which were generally used in the family. This family also possessed one of the largest collections of Mss in medieval Kerala.

Clear and detailed references of the scholars and poets of the Desamangalam family or their works are not available. Some verses found in the beginning of the Mss/Tss of बालबोधिका commentary are the only sources available for such details². All scholars of Kerala

1. Associate Professor, Government Sanskrit College Tripunithura, Eranakulam
2. पारे दक्षिणगङ्गमस्ति महितस्वस्तिप्रदो देहिनाम् देशः कोऽपि शशाङ्कचूडरमणीसान्निध्यनित्योज्वलः ।
वैतानाग्निविलोलधूमपटलीसौगन्ध्यनैरन्तरीमङ्गल्यो जयसिंहमङ्गलमिति क्षोणीसुरैराश्रितः ॥5 ॥
विद्यते तत्र साहित्यविद्याभ्यासरखलूरीका । विश्वपारशवेन्द्रस्य विश्रुतम् भवनोत्तमम् ॥6 ॥
पारम्पर्येण जायन्ते ये तत्र सुकृतोदयात् । आचार्या एव ते सर्वे केरळक्षमाजुषां नृणाम् ॥7 ॥
रुद्राभिधाना तलासीत् भारत्या पुरुषाकृतिः । परक्रोडस्थलाक्रान्तरुद्रतादात्म्यमुद्रिता ॥8 ॥
आपञ्चाशत् समास्सोयं श्रीपञ्चाक्षरजीवनम् । चकारासेव्य साहित्यविद्यां स्वकुलवर्तिनीम् ॥9 ॥
परस्परपमौ शान्तौ तद्वशे सार्वलौकिकौ । श्रीकण्ठाख्यावुभौ जातौ साहित्यैकपरायणौ ॥10 ॥
अथात्मना सुसंवृद्धं देवश्चन्द्रार्धशेखरः । श्रीपरक्रोडवास्तव्यस्तत्कुलं वीक्ष्य हृष्टवान् ॥11 ॥
स तत्र जन्मलाभाय कुतुकी परमेश्वरः । श्रीकण्ठात् पितृतुल्याङ्गो द्वितीयादुदभृत् स्वयम् ॥12 ॥
स बाल्यात् प्रभृति श्रीमान् साहित्यसुरपादपः । अतिगम्भीरवाग्मुम्भसुभगंभावुको बभौ ॥13 ॥

Sanskrit Literature quote these verses only as available source to get any idea regarding the poets and scholars of Desamangalam Variar family and their works.

SKV, a great scholar of the Desamngalam Varriar family, is the author of the commentary BB on शिशुपालधम् । In the prologue of the commentary, SKV makes some references about his family, ancestors, teachers, patrons etc. from the fifth verse onwards. The first four verses are in the form of benediction.

Here it is stated that the author is a native of जयसिंहमङ्गल which is identified as Desamngalam by Ullur (Aiyar 46), Vadakkumkur (Varma 486) and Dr. K.Kunjunni Raja (Raja 111). Desamngalam is a village, situated on the banks of the river Nila near Cheruthurutti in Trichur Dt, Kerala. So the native place of the author may be the same Desamngalam.

The author also refers to a place परक्रोड and the presiding diety there. परक्रोडस्थलाक्रान्त... (V 8) श्रीपरक्रोडवास्तव्यः V 11) परक्रोडेश्वरेच्छया (V18) . According to Ullur this परक्रोड is Triprangode in Malappuram Dt.. God Siva at Triprangode is also referred to here.

The Variyars of Desamangalam family might have had some family connection with Triprangode and it may be due to that God Siva there is also worshipped in these verses as their family deity. One great scholar named Rudra is referred to here. He is said to have lived up to the age of 50 always worshipping his family deity and fully engaged in literary activities (V 9). Two scholars, the names of both being श्रीकण्ठ, were born in the family of Rudra (V 10). The author of the present work is also one श्रीकण्ठ. This श्रीकण्ठ is mentioned here as

श्रीकण्ठाख्य इति स्पष्टनिजाविर्भावकौतुकः । असूत जगतां भूल्यै शिष्यकल्पद्रुमानसौ ॥14 ॥
 ज्ञानेन वाचा वयसा प्रवृद्धत्वमुपेयिवान् । सोऽभजत् पलिताभोगं पुण्याङ्कुरमिवादितम् ॥15 ॥
 यथा यथा वयो यातं तस्य ज्ञानगरीयसः । तथा तथा समायाता स्वच्छता मनसस्तनोः ॥16 ॥
 शीतलीकृतचित्तस्य श्रीकोलूरुगिरीन्द्रजा । प्रविवेशान्तरात्मानं शिवस्येवावस्य निर्वृता ॥17 ॥
 जयसिंहादिमङ्गल्यवास्तव्यश्रीमहेश्वरः । अनेन सौहृदमघात् परक्रोडेश्वरेच्छया ॥18 ॥
 सदाशिवपदाम्भोजभक्तिभाररसायनम् । मूढ्ना वहन्नसावुच्चैरानतोऽपि द्विजान् प्रति ॥19 ॥
 अङ्गस्याङ्गस्य तस्यास्य स्मारं स्मारं कुतूहली । किञ्चु वक्ष्ये ततो जातस्तन्नामाहं सतां मतः ॥20 ॥
 गुरोरनन्तरं सोऽहं कटाक्षेणास्य भूयसा । बालकोऽपि प्रयत्नेन कुलविद्यामुदूढवान् ॥21 ॥
 मनुस्काराम्बुजस्थासु गुरुभूतनियोगतः । अहं पुनर्याज्यशिक्षादक्षो देशिकतामगाम् ॥21 ॥
 गुरोर्नियोगाद्याज्यानां शश्वत्प्रार्थनयापि च । चतुष्टयादिग्रन्थानां व्यख्या बह्व्यः कृता मया ॥23 ॥
 सोऽहं माघकवेः काव्यपारावारतितीर्षया । वितनोमि सुविस्तीर्णां व्याख्यानौकां विचक्षणः ॥24 ॥

the son of the श्रीकण्ठ II referred to above (Vs. 12 and 24).

Thus, there are references to three Srikanthas in this family, श्रीकण्ठ -I, श्रीकण्ठ -II and श्रीकण्ठ- III. श्रीकण्ठ -III is the author of the *BB* commentary of *SV*, the present work and he may be the son of श्रीकण्ठ - II. The father of श्रीकण्ठ - II, श्रीकण्ठ -I is referred to as his preceptor also in the colophone at the end of the commentary of the first canto:

इति श्रीकण्ठाचार्यशिष्येण श्रीकण्ठेन विरचिते बालबोधिकानामनि माघव्याख्याने प्रथमसर्गः ।

A reference to another preceptor of the author is also seen in the above verses in the passage मनुस्काराम्बुजस्थासु गुरुभूतनियोगतः (V.22). Here the meaning of the part of मनुस्काराम्बुजस्थासु is obscure. So no more details about that preceptor could be given here. Dr.K.Kunjunni Raja also has not given any explanation on that passage in the *Contribution of Kerala to Sanskrit Literature* (CKSL) in the context of mentioning *BB* commentary and its author. Similarly the reference to the fact that the author has commented चतुष्टयादिग्रन्थ also remains obscure (Raja 111).

Date of Srikantha

SKV, the author of *BB* commentary, might have lived during the time of the later Zamorins of Calicut. Exact date of the author or the exact name of the ruler under whom he flourished cannot be traced. Vadakkumkur and Dr.K.Kunjunni Raja have mentioned SKV and his *BB* commentary in the context of the discussion of later Zamorins (Raja 110-111). So, one can fix the date of SKV, tentatively in the 16th or 17th century A.D.

However the observation of Ullur.S.Pameswara Iyer that SKV flourished in the 9th century A.D (Aiyar 46) seems to be not documented with sufficient proofs.

Commentary is a medium for understanding and appreciation of the poetic charm integrated within the frame work of the words and phrases of the poem. It may be noted that some such elements are sufficiently pointed out by SKV in *BB*. SKV makes a genuine attempt to lift his readers upto the higher level of poetic appreciation. As a connoisseur the commentator has contributed a lot to the appreciation of the epic, *SV*.

The Nature of The Commentary

The commentary, *BB*, is written in a lucid manner and at the

same time, it has a scholastic touch. The name itself indicates that it is intended for the beginners who desire to enter into the meanings of the Mahakavya. The commentary on each verse begins with a brief introduction to the topic discussed in that particular verse. The full prose order (anvaya) is not seen given. But the main parts constituting the sentence of the verse is usually given in the beginning of the commentary of each verse. The relevant portions of the commentary of the first and second verse of the second canto are given here as an example:

“अथ मुरद्विषन् कार्यद्वयाकुलः आसीदित्यन्वयः ।”

“अथ असौ सदः आसदित्यन्वयः ।”

Then the commentator gives the meaning of each word of the verse in prose order (Anvayakrama). In the commentary, on some verses, a summary of the total idea of the verse is seen given as follows:

ज्ञातसारः अपि विदितवेद्यस्सन्नपि पुरुषान्तरविवेकसहकृतश्चेदनिश्चयैकनिष्ठः स्यादित्यर्थः । (V II-12)

The grammatical peculiarities of the verse, Alankaras, both those of शब्द and अर्थ and other poetic elements are explained in the commentary in almost all verses. Besides, other Sastras like राजनीति, स्मृति and कामशास्त्र are often quoted while explaining the ideas. Kosas or lexicons are also often quoted. Thus, the commentary gives detailed explanation of the poetic, linguistic and other aspects of the verses in a scholarly way. Like almost all other commentaries, the commentary on the first canto is more elaborate compared to that of the other cantos.

SKV is a great scholar in different discipline as well as a good connoisseur. A good connoisseur should have the same aesthetic level of thinking as that of the poet himself (Anandavardhana 38).³ The poetic appreciation of the commentator is evident in many contexts in the commentary. The elaboration of the meaning निशान्तनारीपरिधानधूननस्फुटागसा. . . in the verse 61 of canto I is a good

3 The famous definition of सहृदय of Abhinavagupta is as follows: येषां काव्यानुशीलनाभ्यासवशात् विशदीभूते मनोमुकुरे वर्णनीयतन्मयीभवनयोग्यता ते स्वहृदयसंवादभाजः सहृदयाः ।

example for the poetic appreciation of the commentator. The lower garments of the beautiful ladies in the palace of रावण are raised up by the strong wind. Usually, रावण will not bear the wicked action of the wind. But he did not become angry towards the wind as the lustful lover in रावण was able to see the lower body parts of the beautiful ladies. The explanation of the commentator in this context is as follows:

स हि सर्वतोमुखो दशमुखो यदा कर्यान्तरनिरपेक्षो भार्यानिकरपरिवृतस्वैरासिका
मासेवते स्म तदा नर्मसचिवधुरन्धरोऽयं प्रकम्पनः तत्कटाक्षकोणाकूतसर्वस्वपरमार्थज्ञ
स्तासां परिधानपटवेष्टनमुत्थापयामास सक्थिमूलदृष्टिसौकर्यसम्पादनाय इत्येवं रूपोऽर्थो
निशान्तनारीपरिधानधूननेति पदेन विवक्षितः ।

As mentioned earlier, in the first and second canto, the commentator gives the meanings of some words of the verses in Malayalam language. In some places, a brief summary of the verse in Malayalam is also found given. This is a strange practice found in Sanskrit Commentaries and it is not seen continued from third canto onwards.

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